

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 GENERAL

The machine learning is defined as the one in which the machine is trained and tested. The machine learning has two phases as the training phase and the testing phase. There are three types of machine learning as Supervised learning, Unsupervised learning and Reinforcement learning. The Supervised learning is defined as the sample dataset is given to the machine by the user for training. The Unsupervised Learning is defined as the machine itself considers the dataset on its own. The Reinforcement Learning is defined as the one in which it is a machine learning training method based on rewarding desired behaviors and punishing undesired ones. Malicious code injection is defined as the one in which it occurs when an attacker exploits an input validation flaw in system to inject malicious code. There are some types of malicious code injection attacking types, the two of them are Co-visitation injection attack and Profile injection attack. The Co-visitation injection attack is defined as the attack in which the attackers or hackers keep on viewing the website but without buying a product, the attackers will give a review for product in a website. The Profile injection attack is defined as the attack in which the attackers or hackers give a review for a product in a website through fake user identity. This proposed paper, is based on the Machine Learning algorithms where the sample dataset is trained to the machine and then tested for seeking the result or the output.

1.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY

The need for the protection of the people or the users from trusting the malicious reviews given for the product in the web applications, is to detect and eliminate those malicious reviews injected. These malicious reviews are the malicious code injected reviews which are used for the attacking purpose in reviews by the attackers. These attackers or the hackers create those malicious code injected reviews. The malicious code injected reviews are injected by the attackers or the hackers when the website service is low in the web applications. Hence these malicious injection attacked reviews are detected and eliminated by using the Natural Language Processing (NLP) technique. This technique can be applied for the elimination of the unwanted disturbed data's in the web applications. Naïve Bayes Classifier (NBC) algorithm can be implemented for the classification of the objects. Here this particular algorithm is applied for the classification of the given user input reviews into good reviews and bad reviews. This algorithm is one of the Supervised Machine Learning algorithms. This algorithm applied is very fast in accuracy and can be used to make the real time predictions easily. For easy understanding of the reviews which are in the sample dataset the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm is used. This PCA algorithm is often used as the dimensionality-reduction technique. Here this algorithm is implemented for reducing the length of the reviews in the sample dataset. And also this algorithm is one of the Machine Learning algorithms.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Malicious reviews detection and elimination mainly aims to protect the people or the users from trusting the malicious code injected reviews and also the user input review is classified into good review and bad review. There are some types of malicious injection attacks, the two of them are Co-visitation injection attack and Profile injection attack. The pre-processing aims at the elimination of the disturbed data which are the malicious injection attacked reviews. By enhancing the profile injection behaviors and co-visitation injection behaviors the disturbed data is eliminated. And also the sentiment identification of the reviews in the sample dataset is done, which identifies the reviews emotions as whether the review sentiment is kind of positive or negative or malicious. The central aim of the PCA (Principal Component Analysis) is the dimensionality-reduction of the reviews in the sample dataset. In which the length of the reviews are reduced into a easier format for easy understanding. The advantage of PCA is that it improves the visualization of the data and has high performance speed and hence works fast. And the constraint number is also fixed according to the sample dataset given to the machine for training. The main focus for the NBC (Naïve Bayes Classifier) is to classify the objects. In which here, the user input reviews are compared with the sample dataset given for training the machine and then classified as positive(good) review and negative(bad) review and also detected as malicious or not. It is also compared with the five other algorithms to calculate the accuracy value of the algorithm. The advantage of NBC is that it has the highest accuracy value.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 IMPLEMENTATION OF NAIVE BAYES CLASSIFIER ALGORITHM ON SOCIAL MEDIA (TWITTER) TO THE TEACHING OF INDONESIAN HATE SPEECH

Twitter is a social media that is widely used as a sharing medium on the internet. There are tweets containing sentences shared by the user, thus they can be read by the other users. A lot of information can be obtained from Twitter. Twitter users can connect with the other Twitter users in an international scale. Technology that is growing as today can be used for various things, especially regarding the information distributed in social media, specifically Twitter. One of the problems derived from social media is that Twitter tweets containing speeches in the form of both positive and negative utterances. From the problems above, a research is required to classify tweets that contain positive and negative speeches or utterances using naive bayes classifier method. The results of this study are implemented into a system that can classify tweets on Twitter. The system is built using is Node technology and Naive Bayes classifier as the calculation method of classification. Based on the tests performed, the best accuracy generated by the systems using the Naive Bayes Classifier is 93%.

2.2 EFFICIENT AUTHOR COMMUNITY GENERATION ON NLP BASED RELEVANCE FEATURE DETECTION

Many researchers provided different feature discovery techniques, but that shows high time complexity according to the LDA process. It does not provide any user preference for document search history, to avoid this problem a NLP technique is used. NLP provides maximum pattern for search input so it generates maximum pattern output. Ranking of each document is according to the new patterns that generated from NLP. Community generation of documents will be done based on the cluster information; It will help document users to find other documents in the domain. Cluster the whole documents using the technique and applying the advanced ranking. So that the advanced ranking of the relevant feature produces the author community generation process so that authors can communicate each other. In order to make faster searching and more data availability the NLP based searching is used. Natural language Processing (NLP) is the ability of a computer program to understand human speech as it is spoken. NLP is a component of artificial intelligence. The development of NLP applications is challenging because computers traditionally require humans to “speak” to them in a programming language that is precise, unambiguous and highly structured or, perhaps through a limited number of clearly-enunciated voice commands. The NLP based search is giving more information and the author community generation is also produced. So that the authors can communicate each other.

2.3 NAIVE BAYES CLASSIFIERS FOR MUSIC EMOTION CLASSIFICATION BASED ON LYRICS

There is a constantly growing interest in evaluating music information retrieval (MIR) systems that can provide effective management of the music resources. The crucial characteristic of music is its emotion, which reflect the human's perception. To do the automatic classification of Chinese music emotions more effective, we use the lyrics of music to analysis and classify music based on emotion. There are many algorithms to achieve text classification, and one of the most popular algorithms is Naive Bayes algorithm. Although it is simple, it can classify text effectively. In this paper, we crawl the music lyrics and their labels from a popular website named Baidu music and make our four different datasets. We also train four classifiers with different datasets and report their performance. We evaluate the classifiers trained by four different datasets, and the final accuracy we get is approximately 68%. Naive Bayes classification is based on the assumption that the principle of maximum posteriori hypothesis to identify the object that most likely to be classified under the category. Bayes theorem shows the relation between one conditional probability and its inverse. we assume that the words of the lyrics are independent and of equal weight. Finally, using the above formula, we can get the conditional probability of each category, of which the biggest one is the category of the sample. The Naive Bayesian Classifier is a classification algorithm that is easy to implement. Owe to its simplicity of the model and the good classification performance, it's widely used in engineering application.

2.4 ADAPTIVE SIGNAL PROCESSING ALGORITHM FOR REMOTE DETECTION OF HEART RATE (HR) USING ULTRA-WIDEBAND WAVEFORMS BASED ON PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

Ultra-Wideband (UWB) technology provides a convenient approach for remote biomedical sensing and vital signs monitoring in humans. In this paper, a specific algorithm is proposed to improve the ability of Heart Rate (HR) detection. Unlike previous methods for remote HR detection, the proposed method provides an adaptive filter based on respiration and heart rate parameters obtained from UWB waveforms. The algorithm is capable of detecting heart rate by changing the adaptive filter parameters accordingly. The proposed method is employed on real life data collected by UWB transceiver. According to experiments, it is concluded that the proposed technique is able to handle remote detection of different heart rates accurately. Ultra-wideband (UWB) waveforms are in the range of microwave and are used at very low energy levels for short range high-bandwidth communications. For this technology, transmitted information spread over large bandwidth (in the range of gigahertz). The use of UWB signals has been suggested for several medical applications because of the high spatial resolution provided by ultra-wideband signals. For an UWB antenna setup, the motion of a human body can cause significant changes to the UWB waveforms. Some advantages of UWB waveforms are the large bandwidth, convenient material penetration and extras.

2.5 IMPLEMENTATION OF NAÏVE BAYES CLASSIFIER ALGORITHM TO CATEGORIZE INDONESIAN SONG LYRICS BASED ON AGE

The rapid development of technology accelerates the process of distributing the song in Indonesia. But that songs have not been followed by the age label of the listener, such as the age label on the movie. It certainly makes people difficult to choose songs that appropriate to their age, so people are free to enjoy a variety of songs and probably will earn the bad effect to the mental development. Therefore, there need to classify the lyrics of Indonesian language songs according to the age of the community. Several types of research classify song by its genre like pop, rock, jazz, i.e., classify by emotion of the song, and region of the song. In this study, develops a system that can categorize the lyrics into four age groups of the listener, namely children, adolescents, adults and all ages using naïve bayes classifier (NBC) algorithm with the number of datasets are 400 titles obtained through crawling on lirik.kapanlagi.com website. The testing algorithm using training data of 60, 70, 80, and 90 percent from the overall dataset with equitable distribution resulted accuracies are 62.5%, 65%, 67.5%, and 67.5% respectively. Document classification process with naïve bayes classifier is presenting each document with attributes “ $x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, \dots, x_n$ ” which mean that x_1 is first word, x_2 is second word, and so on. For a set of words V . When performing the document classification process, naïve bayes classifier will search the highest probability value from all categories of documents tested (Vmap).

2.6 COMPRESSION OF LARGE-SCALE IMAGE DATASET USING PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS AND K-MEANS CLUSTERING

Digital images, being on the verge of its utmost popularity encompasses plenty of applications and as such are generated at an unprecedented rate. These digital form of data are often found with redundant information. Applications that require a bulk amount of images to be processed, turn out to be high regarding computational complexity. Needless to say, it leads to inefficient storage utilization. In this paper, a hybrid approach is applied to compress a large-scale image data-set by combining two popular algorithms: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and K-means. This paper works with a view to diminishing the redundant information by implementing dimensionality reduction followed by color quantization. The PCA is used to project the data onto a lower dimensional space with retaining as maximum variance as possible. The K-means algorithm is used to restrict the distinct number of colors to represent an image by means of clustering the data together. The results obtained from the proposed method is compared with the results obtained from implementing PCA and K-means clustering algorithms independently, where the proposed method provides with a better compression ratio. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is one of the most used statistical techniques, which works with the perception obtained from a large quantity of numerical data depending on the correlation amongst the variables.

2.7 FORMATION OF SQL FROM NATURAL LANGUAGE QUERY USING NLP

Today, everyone has their own personal devices that connects to the internet. Every user tries to get the information that they require through internet. Most of the information is in the form of a database. A user who wants to access a database but having limited or no knowledge of database languages faces a challenging and difficult situation. Hence, there is a need for a system that enables the users to access the information in the database. This paper aims to develop such a system using NLP by giving structured natural language question as input and receiving SQL query as the output, to access the related information from the railways reservation database with ease. The steps involved in this process are tokenization, lemmatization, parts of speech tagging, parsing and mapping. The dataset used for the proposed system has a set of 2880 structured natural language queries on train fare and seats available. We have achieved 98.89 per cent accuracy. The paper would give an overall view of the usage of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and use of regular expressions to map the query in English language to SQL. To find a solution for such a problem and facilitate human interaction with computers, Natural Language Processing(NLP) techniques are used. Natural Language Processing has applications in various sectors like tourism, where a tourist can get information about the famous tourist spots in a particular city, the hotels available, best restaurants nearby etc. Another important application of NLP is chatbot (Chat Robot) that can be used for voice or textual interactions.

2.8 MULTIVARIATE STATISTICAL DATA ANALYSIS- PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS (PCA)

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a multivariate technique that analyzes a data table in which observations are described by several inter-correlated quantitative dependent variables. Its goal is to extract the important information from the statistical data to represent it as a set of new orthogonal variables called principal components, and to display the pattern of similarity between the observations and of the variables as points in spot maps. Mathematically, PCA depends upon the eigen-decomposition of positive semi-definite matrices and upon the singular value decomposition (SVD) of rectangular matrices. It is determined by eigenvectors and eigenvalues. Eigenvectors and eigenvalues are numbers and vectors associated to square matrices. Together they provide the eigen-decomposition of a matrix, which analyzes the structure of this matrix such as correlation, covariance, or cross-product matrices. Performing PCA is quite simple in practice. Organize a data set as an $m \times n$ matrix, where m is the number of measurement types and n is the number of trials. Subtract of the mean for each measurement type or row x_i . Calculate the SVD or the eigenvectors of the covariance. It was found that there were many interesting applications of PCA, out of which in day today life knowingly or unknowingly multivariate data analysis and image compression are being used alternatively. Principal component analysis is the oldest and best known technique of multivariate data analysis.

2.9 MOBILE BASED DATA RETRIEVAL USING RDF AND NLP IN AN EFFICIENT APPROACH

Nowadays Youngsters like IT people and various sectors are showing massive interest and moving towards agriculture farming for self sustainable energy for our generation. People are in metro environment with family owned lands they are in need of proper guidance from farmers having huge experience But there is a gap in medium in approaching the farmers by staying with them for months together to get Knowledge Transfer for facing issues and clarifications. The farmers and ancestors traditional methods and subject knowledge need to be transferred to upcoming generations. In Digital world, farmers are using smart phones so to document the knowledge from farmers the Subject Matter Expertise of agriculture (SME) under database and to provide solution by queries in efficient approach through RDF (Resource Description Framework) and Natural Language Processing Technique (NLP) in the form of mobile application internally using SPARQL queries. In this paper, WordNet text mining processing method is used. NLP reduces the gap between computer and human by combining the database query into meaningful forms. Hence system manipulates semantic analysis. Here WordNet Processing – wordset is used for identifying the semantic similarities in the words of the dataset. It groups the semantically identical words to the word of interest. While most Android applications are written in Java, there is no Java Virtual Machine in the platform and Java byte code is not executed.

2.10 JOB SEEKER PROFILE CLASSIFICATION OF TWITTER DATA USING THE NAÏVE BAYES CLASSIFIER ALGORITHM BASED ON THE DISC METHOD

Human resource staff in a company is a person in charge of finding new workers. To get a qualified new workforce, a human resource staff must be selective toward the appliance in terms of ability and personality. This study provides an alternative perspective for a human resource in getting one's personality data through their tweets on a Twitter account. This study uses the Naive Bayes Classifier algorithm with W-IDF (Weighted-Inverse Document Frequency) weighting to classify the personality of recruits into one of DISC's personality theories, namely Dominance, Influence, Steadiness, and Compliance. By using training data and test data as many as 120 personal Twitter accounts and labelling of words that have been verified by psychologists, obtained personality distribution. The classification of the tweet data is Dominance 90 accounts, Influence 10 accounts, Steadiness 8 accounts and Compliance 12 accounts. Evaluation of the accuracy level of 36.67%. Twitter is a social media that allow people to establish communication between users and get the latest information or news. Only by making a tweet, Twitter users can directly share any information. According to records compiled, there are 150 million active internet users in Indonesia and of that number, there are 6.43 million active Twitter users.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The main reason for this project is that the people or the users when buying a product in the website, they mainly see the reviews for their reference and for knowing about the product. In that case when they see the reviews they unknowingly considers the malicious reviews also as the reviews given by the original users and they judge and come to a decision about the product, since these malicious reviews are mixed with the original users reviews. These malicious reviews are the malicious code injected reviews by the attackers through the malicious injection attacks when the website service is low. Malicious code injection is defined as occurring when an attacker exploits an input validation flaw in system to inject malicious code. There are some types of malicious code injection attacking types, the two of them as follows. The Co-visitation injection attack is defined as the attackers or hackers keep on viewing the website but without buying a product, the attackers will give a review for product in a website. The Profile injection attack is defined as the attackers or hackers give a review for a product in a website through fake user identity. Hence to overcome this problem, this project is proposed. The main goal of this project is to save the users or the people from trusting these malicious reviews. By using Naïve Bayes Classifier (NBC) algorithm which has highest accuracy, the reviews are identified as good or bad and also detected as malicious or not.

3.2 CONCEPT

In the proposed system, the sentiment data's that is the unwanted disturbed data's are first eliminated from the given dataset by using the Natural Language Processing (NLP) technique. Secondly the constraint number is fixed according to the given sample, hence the dimensionality of the given dataset is reduced and the important data alone is extracted using the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Finally, the input is given which is compared with the sample dataset and by using the Naive Bayes Classifier (NBC), it is classified into fake reviews and original reviews in which the original reviews are further classified as positive (good) and negative (bad) which is displayed with the algorithm accuracy percentage value. The Eliminating Noise Data in Website (ENDW) technique eliminates the noisy data with a greater efficiency. The Natural Language Processing (NLP) technique has higher rate of sentiment identification. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm improves the visualization of the data and has high performance speed and hence works fast. NBC algorithm is defined as the one which is an algorithm that is used for the classification of the objects is called as NBC algorithm. The Naïve Bayes Classifier (NBC) algorithm is the algorithm that has the higher algorithm accuracy value.

3.3 METHODOLOGIES

3.3.1 PRE PROCESSING

In preprocessing stage, first the training of the machine is done. This comes under the training phase in machine learning. This machine training is done by collecting the dataset from any of the web applications such as Amazon, extras. And this dataset for training the machine which is taken from the data source called as the kaggle. Then the enhancement of Profile injection behaviours and Co-visitation injection behaviours is done. By enhancing the profile injection behaviors and co-visitation injection behaviors the disturbed data is eliminated. The malicious code injected reviews are injected by the attackers or the hackers when the website service is low in the web applications. Malicious code injection is defined as the one in which it occurs when an attacker exploits an input validation flaw in system to inject malicious code. There are some types of malicious code injection attacking types, the two of them are Co-visitation injection attack and Profile injection attack. There are fake user identities that are created by the attackers, through sending continuous links to some user till the user clicks on that link. When user clicks the link, that particular users identity will be stolen by the attackers which is done like the phishing. Generally these reviews which are maliciously injected are mixed with the original users review of the product in a website. The disturbed data is eliminated by using the Natural Language Processing (NLP) technique. Natural Language Processing has applications in various sectors like tourism, where a tourist can get information about the famous tourist spots in a particular city, the

hotels available, best restaurants nearby etc. Another important application of NLP is chatbot (Chat Robot) that can be used for voice or textual interactions. The goal is a computer capable of "understanding" the contents of documents, including the contextual nuances of the language within them. The technology can then accurately extract information and insights contained in the documents as well as categorize and organize the documents themselves. NLP reduces the gap between computer and human by combining the database query into meaningful forms. Natural Language Processing (NLP) technique is defined as the one in which it is used to eliminate the disturbed data in the websites. In simple words, the steps involved in this elimination process using NLP technique are as follows,

Step 1 : First the meaning of given input reviews from the dataset are analyzed for better machine understanding.

Step 2 : Then the arrangement of the review words from the dataset are done.

Step 3 : The disturbed data like symbols, meaningless words, extra characters are separated in the input dataset given.

Step 4 : Then finally, those separated data's are removed or eliminated from the input dataset given.

3.3.2 FEATURE EXTRACTION

In feature extraction stage, first the constraint number is fixed according to the given sample training dataset in the preprocessing stage. Hence after the removal of disturbed data in the preprocessing stage, the remaining

dataset is given as the input to this feature extraction stage. Then the dimensionality of the given dataset is reduced that is the length of each review in the dataset is minimized for easy understanding. Hence the important data alone is extracted using the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is often used as the dimensionality-reduction technique. Principal component analysis (PCA) is the process of computing the principal components and using them to perform a change of basis on the data, sometimes using only the first few principal components and ignoring the rest. PCA is used in exploratory data analysis and for making predictive models. PCA is defined as an orthogonal linear transformation that transforms the data to a new coordinate system such that the greatest variance by some scalar projection of the data comes to lie on the first coordinate (called the first principal component), the second greatest variance on the second coordinate, and so on. In simple words, the steps involved in this dimensionality-reduction process using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm are as follows,

Step 1 : First the dataset which is the output from the preprocessing module is collected.

Step 2 : The data headings from the dataset are first listed for machine reference.

Step 3 : Then the unwanted data heading are alone spotted separately.

Step 4 : Finally, those unwanted data heading are then removed to reduce the length of the dataset for machine easy understanding.

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm improves the visualization of the data. The PCA algorithm also has the high performance speed. And hence the PCA algorithm works fast. The Principal Component Analysis improves the performance of the Machine Learning algorithm. The Principal Component Analysis results in the high variance and thus improves the visualization. PCA algorithm is one of the Machine Learning algorithms.

3.3.3 CLASSIFICATION

In classification stage, the review is given as the input for the classification of output. This input review which is given, is compared with the sample dataset which is the output of the feature extraction module. After the comparison is done, the input review is classified either as an positive (good) or as an negative (bad) and also detected as malicious or not by using the Naive Bayes Classifier (NBC) algorithm. The Naïve Bayes Classifier algorithm is defined as the one which is an algorithm that is used for the classification of the objects is called as NBC algorithm. Naïve Bayes classifiers are highly scalable, requiring a number of parameters linear in the number of variables (features/predictors) in a learning problem. Naive Bayes is a simple technique for constructing classifiers and models that assign class labels to problem instances, represented as vectors of feature values, where the class labels are drawn from some finite set. There is not a single algorithm for training such classifiers, but a family of algorithms based on a common principle: all naive Bayes classifiers assume that the value of a particular feature is independent of the value of any other feature, given the class variable. For example, a fruit may

be considered to be an apple if it is red, round, and about 10 cm in diameter. NBC algorithm is one of the supervised Machine Learning algorithms. The independent feature model that is, the naïve Bayes probability model. The naïve Bayes classifier combines this model with a decision rule. One common rule is to pick the hypothesis that is most probable; this is known as the maximum a posteriori or MAP decision rule. In simple words, the Naïve Bayes Classifier(NBC) algorithm working procedure in steps are as follows,

Step 1 : In train classifier, after giving the sample dataset into the machine, the machine forms the unique words from the dataset given.

Step 2 : Machine then also forms the frequency of each word in a document from the unique words formed.

Step 3 : Now after this, machine removes the unwanted words by referring from the dictionary of stop words.

Step 4 : Then if negative label, then calculate the probabilities for negative. If positive label, then calculate the probabilities for positive. If malicious label, then calculate the probabilities for malicious.

Step 4.1 : For the probability calculation of each class such as positive, negative and malicious :

Step 4.1.1 : First taking the positive outcomes.

Step 4.1.2 : Then computing the probability for each unique words in positive label by using the formula,

$$P(w_k/+) = \frac{(n_k+1)}{n} + \frac{1}{|Vocabulary|}$$

Where,

n_k : Number of times word k occurs in positive case.

n : Number of words in positive.

Vocabulary : Total unique words.

Step 4.1.3 : Repeating the step 4.1.2 for negative label and malicious label.

Step 4.1.4 : While testing for unknown words, then $n_k = 0$ is used and its probability is found for all positive, negative, malicious labels.

Step 5 : In test classifier, the input test data is given into the machine.

Step 6 : Now repeating the step 3 for the input test data given.

Step 7 : Comparing each reviews in the input test data with the trained dataset labels, and separating the reviews into positive label, negative label and malicious label.

Step 8 : Now probability for each reviews in all three labels are calculated.

Step 9 : Now, adding all the review probabilities of each label to get the total values of each class.

Step 10 : After adding, the classification is done now and the total value of each class is displayed, which is the final output result.

The Naïve Bayes Classifier(NBC) algorithm is compared with the few other algorithms to calculate the accuracy value of the algorithm. The Naïve Bayes Classifier algorithm which is used in the proposed system has the higher algorithm accuracy value up to 0.9. The Naïve Bayes Classifier is simple and easy to implement and it handles both continuous and discrete data's. The NBC is very fast in accuracy and can be used to make real time predictions.

3.4 DESIGN

Fig 3.4 System Architecture

3.5 MODELING

Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a general purpose modelling language. The main aim of UML is to define a standard way to visualize the way a system has been designed. It is quite similar to blueprints used in other fields of engineering. UML is not a programming language, it is rather a visual language. We use UML diagrams to portray the behavior and structure of a system. UML helps software engineers, businessmen and system architects with modelling, design and analysis.

3.5.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM

Fig 3.5.1 Use Case Diagram

3.5.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

Fig 3.5.2 Sequence Diagram

3.5.3 CLASS DIAGRAM

Fig 3.5.3 Class Diagram

3.5.4 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

Fig 3.5.4 Activity Diagram

3.5.5 COLLABORATION DIAGRAM

Fig 3.5.5 Collaboration Diagram

3.5.6 STATE CHART DIAGRAM

Fig 3.5.6 State Chart Diagram

CHAPTER 4

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The requirement specification is a technical specification of requirements of the software products. It is the first step in the requirement analysis process, its lists the requirements of a particular software system include functional, performance. The requirements also provide usage scenario from the user, an operational and an administrative perspective. The purpose of software requirements specification is to provide a detailed overview of the software project, its parameter and goals. This describes the project target audience and its user interface, hardware and software requirements.

4.1.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The most common set of requirements defined by any operating system or software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware, A hardware requirements list is often accompanied by a hardware compatibility list (HCL), especially in case of operating systems. An HCL lists tested, compatible, and sometimes incompatible hardware devices for a particular operating system or application. The following sub-sections discuss the various aspects of hardware requirements.

- Processor : AMD A6
- Memory : 64-bit processor

- RAM : 4 GB
- Hard Disk : 150 GB

4.1.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software requirements deal with defining software resource requirements and prerequisites that need to be installed on a computer to provide optimal functioning of an application. These requirements or prerequisites are generally not included in the software installation package and need to be installed separately before the software is installed.

- Operating system : Windows 10
- Tool: Anaconda (Jupyter Notebook)
- Front End: Python
- Browser : Flask

4.2 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

4.2.1 PYTHON

Python is an interpreted high-level general-purpose programming language. Its design philosophy emphasizes code readability with its use of significant indentation. Its language constructs as well as its object-oriented approach aim to help programmers write clear, logical code for small and large-scale projects. Python is dynamically-typed and garbage-collected. It also supports the more multiple code with the multiple programming paradigms, including structured (particularly, procedural), object-oriented and functional

programming. It is often described as a "batteries included" language due to its comprehensive standard library. Guido van Rossum began working on Python in the late 1980s, as a successor to the ABC programming language, and first released it in 1991 as Python 0.9.0. Python 2.0 was released in 2000 and introduced new features, such as list comprehensions and a cycle-detecting garbage collection system (in addition to reference counting). Python 3.0 was released in 2008 and was a major revision of the language that is not completely backward-compatible. Python 2 was discontinued with version 2.7.18 in 2020. Python consistently ranks as one of the most popular programming languages.

4.2.2 PYTHON PLATFORM

Python defines an in-built module platform that provides system information. The Platform module is used to retrieve as much possible information about the platform on which the program is being currently executed. Now by platform info, it means information about the device, it's OS, node, OS version, Python version, etc. This module plays a crucial role when you want to check whether your program is compatible with the python version installed on a particular system or whether the hardware specifications meet the requirements of your program. This module already exists in the python library and does not require any installation using pip.

4.2.3 ANACONDA

Anaconda is said as distribution of the Python and R programming languages for scientific computing (data science, machine learning applications, large-scale data processing, predictive analytics, etc.), that aims to simplify package management and deployment. The distribution includes data-science packages suitable for Windows, Linux, and macOS. It is developed and maintained by Anaconda, Inc., which was founded by Peter Wang and Travis Oliphant in 2012. As an Anaconda, Inc. product, it is also known as Anaconda Distribution or Anaconda Individual Edition, while other products from the company are Anaconda Team Edition and Anaconda Enterprise Edition, both of which are not free. Package versions in Anaconda are managed by the package management system conda. This package manager was spun out as a separate open-source package as it ended up being useful on its own and for things other than Python. There is also a small, bootstrap version of Anaconda called Miniconda, which includes only conda, Python, the packages they depend on, and a small number of other packages.

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM TESTING

5.1 TESTING OBJECTIVES

Software testing is a crucial element in the software development life cycle (SDLC), which can help software engineers save time & money of organizations by finding errors and defects during the early stages of software development. With the assistance of this process one can examine various components associated with the application and guarantee their appropriateness. The goals and objectives of software testing are numerous, which when achieved help developers build a defect-less and error free software and application that has exceptional performance, quality, effectiveness, security, among other things. Though the objective of testing can vary from company to company and project to project, there are some goals that are similar for all. The benefits and advantages offered by software testing are innumerable. It helps software developers and programmers in verifying and validating various components of the software as well as in detecting bugs and defects. Moreover, it helps them deliver a software product that has remarkable quality and innovative features.

Type of Testing

There are two types of testing according their behaviours. They are:

1. Unconventional Testing
2. Conventional Testing

Unconventional Testing

Unconventional testing is a process of verification which is done by software quality assurance team. It is a prevention technique which is performing from beginning to ending of the project development. In this process SQA team verifies project development activities and insuring that developing project is fulfilling the requirement of the client or not.

Conventional Testing

Conventional testing is a process of finding the bugs and validating the project. Testing team involves in this testing process and validating that developed project is according to client requirement or not. This process is a correction technique where testing team bugs and reporting to the development team for correction on developed project built.

5.2 TEST CASE DESIGN

5.2.1 Unit Testing

Unit tests are typically automated tests written and run by software developers to ensure that a section of an application (known as the "unit") meets its design and behaves as intended. In procedural programming, a unit could be an entire module, but it is more commonly an individual function or procedure. In object-oriented programming, a unit is often an entire interface, such as a class, or an individual method. By writing tests first for the smallest testable units, then the compound behaviors between those, one can build up

comprehensive tests for complex applications. To isolate issues that may arise, each test case should be tested independently. Substitutes such as method stubs, mock objects, fakes, and test harnesses can be used to assist testing a module in isolation.

5.2.2 Functional Testing

Functional testing is a quality assurance (QA) process and a type of black-box testing that bases its test cases on the specifications of the software component under test. Functions are tested by feeding them input and examining the output, and internal program structure is rarely considered (unlike white-box testing). Functional testing is conducted to evaluate the compliance of a system or component with specified functional requirements. Functional testing usually describes what the system does. Since functional testing is a type of black-box testing, the software's functionality can be tested without knowing the internal workings of the software. This means that testers do not need to know programming languages or how the software has been implemented. This, in turn, could lead to reduced developer bias (or confirmation bias) in testing since the tester has not been involved in the software's development. Functional testing does not imply that you are testing a function (method) of your module or class. Functional testing tests a slice of functionality of the whole system.

5.2.3 System Testing

System testing is testing conducted on a complete integrated system to evaluate the system's compliance with its specified requirements. System testing

takes, as its input, all of the integrated components that have passed integration testing. The purpose of integration testing is to detect any inconsistencies between the units that are integrated together. System testing seeks to detect defects both within the "inter-assemblages" and also within the system as a whole. The actual result is the behavior produced or observed when a component or system is tested. System testing is performed on the entire system in the context of either functional requirement specifications (FRS) or system requirement specification (SRS), or both. System testing tests not only the design, but also the behaviour and even the believed expectations of the customer. It is also intended to test up to and beyond the bounds defined in the software or hardware requirements specification(s).

5.2.4 Acceptance Testing

Acceptance testing is a test conducted to determine if the requirements of specification or contract are met. It may involve chemical tests, physical tests, or performance tests. In systems engineering, it may involve black-box testing performed on a system (for example: a piece of software, lots of manufactured mechanical parts, or batches of chemical products) prior to its delivery. Acceptance testing is also known as user acceptance testing (UAT), end-user testing.

CHAPTER 6

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First and foremost the machine has been successfully trained. And then the malicious code injected reviews are been detected by using the Naïve Bayes Classifier algorithm. Then the disturbed data in the review are eliminated by using NLP technique. Mainly the affected malicious review is successfully detected by using the NBC algorithm. Hence the main goal of saving the people or users from unknowingly trusting the malicious code injected reviews has been successfully achieved. This NBC algorithm used for classification process for the detection of reviews as good or bad and also as malicious or not, has the higher algorithm accuracy detection rate value up to 0.9.

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The Detection of malicious injection attack in reviews with algorithms high accuracy value is proposed in this paper. This proposed paper also detects the type of the review from the given input review whether it is positive(good) review or negative(bad) review and also detected as malicious or not. We train the machine in this paper by giving the sample datasets, hence the machine compares the input with the trained datasets and provide the output result. The algorithm used in this paper for the classification of output results as good or bad and is malicious or not, the accuracy value is calculated by comparing it with few algorithms to show our used algorithm in the proposed system has the highest accuracy value. The further enhancement process of the project is that the malicious code injected Uniform Resource Locator which is the expansion of URL that is the Links of the web applications can be identified. And then can also be detected as whether the uniform resource locator of the web applications are malicious or not in the near future.

APPENDICES

A. SAMPLE CODE

```
//Import Libraries

#Basic libraries

import pandas as pd

import numpy as np

#NLTK libraries

import nltk

import re

import string

from wordcloud import WordCloud,STOPWORDS

from nltk.stem.porter import PorterStemmer

from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer

# Machine Learning libraries

import sklearn

from sklearn.svm import SVC

from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder

from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler

from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler

from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier

from sklearn.pipeline import make_pipeline

from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV

from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression

from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier

from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier

from sklearn.naive_bayes import BernoulliNB

from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier

from sklearn.multiclass import OneVsRestClassifier
```

```
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.pipeline import Pipeline
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import label_binarize
from sklearn import svm, datasets
from sklearn import preprocessing
#Metrics libraries
from sklearn import metrics
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.metrics import roc_auc_score
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve, auc
#Visualization libraries
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib import rcParams
import seaborn as sns
from textblob import TextBlob
from plotly import tools
import plotly.graph_objs as go
from plotly.offline import iplot
%matplotlib inline
#Ignore warnings
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
#Other miscellaneous libraries
from scipy import interp
from itertools import cycle
import cufflinks as cf
```

```

from collections import defaultdict
from collections import Counter
from imblearn.over_sampling import SMOTE

//Import Dataset

raw_reviews =
pd.read_csv(r'C:\Users\baska\sentiment\Musical_instruments_reviews.csv')

## print shape of dataset with rows and columns and information
print ("The shape of the data is (row, column):" + str(raw_reviews.shape))
print (raw_reviews.info())

raw_reviews.head()

//Modules

//Preprocessing

# Disturbed data Elimination
import nltk

from nltk.corpus import brown as cb
from nltk.corpus import gutenberg as cg

#Creating a copy
process_reviews=raw_reviews.copy()

#Checking for null values
process_reviews.isnull().sum()

process_reviews['reviewText']=process_reviews['reviewText'].fillna('Missing')

#Review text punctuation cleaning

#Removing unnecessary columns

process_reviews=process_reviews.drop(['reviewerName','unixReviewTime'],
axis=1)

#Creating a copy
clean_reviews=process_reviews.copy()

def review_cleaning(text):

```

```

    """Make text lowercase, remove text in square brackets,remove links,remove
punctuation
and remove words containing numbers."""
text = str(text).lower()
text = re.sub('\[.*?\]', "", text)
text = re.sub('https?://\S+|www.\S+', "", text)
text = re.sub('<.*?>+', "", text)
text = re.sub('[%s]' % re.escape(string.punctuation), "", text)
text = re.sub('\n', "", text)
text = re.sub('\w*\d\w*', "", text)
return text
process_reviews.head()
//Feature Extraction
# Dimensionality Reduction
# contacting review text and summary
process_reviews['reviews']=process_reviews['reviewText']+process_reviews['s
ummary']
process_reviews=process_reviews.drop(['reviewText', 'summary'], axis=1)
process_reviews.head()
# handling time column
# new data frame which has date and year
new = process_reviews["reviewTime"].str.split(" ", n = 1, expand = True)
# making separate date column from new data frame
process_reviews["date"]= new[0]
# making separate year column from new data frame
process_reviews["year"]= new[1]
process_reviews=process_reviews.drop(['reviewTime'], axis=1)
process_reviews.head()
from sklearn.decomposition import PCA

```

```

pca = PCA(n_components=None)
# Splitting the date
new1 = process_reviews["date"].str.split(" ", n = 1, expand = True)
# adding month to the main dataset
process_reviews["month"]= new1[0]
# adding day to the main dataset
process_reviews["day"]= new1[1]
process_reviews=process_reviews.drop(['date'], axis=1)
process_reviews.head()
# Review text length distribution graph
process_reviews['review_len'].iplot(
    kind='hist',
    bins=100,
    xTitle='review length',
    linecolor='black',
    yTitle='count',
    title='Review Text Length Distribution')
//Classification
class NaiveBayes:
    def __init__(self,unique_classes):
        self.classes=unique_classes # Constructor is simply passed with unique
number of classes of the training set
    def addToBow(self,example,dict_index):
        """ Parameters:
        1. example
        2. dict_index - implies to which BoW category this example belongs to
        What the function does?
        -----

```

It simply splits the example on the basis of space as a tokenizer and adds every tokenized word to

its corresponding dictionary/BoW

Returns:

Nothing"

```
if isinstance(example,np.ndarray): example=example[0]
```

```
for token_word in example.split(): #for every word in preprocessed example
```

```
self.bow_dicts[dict_index][token_word]+=1 #increment in its count
```

```
def train(self,dataset,labels):
```

```
    """ Parameters:
```

```
        1. dataset - shape = (m X d)
```

```
        2. labels - shape = (m,)
```

```
    What the function does?
```

```
    -----
```

This is the training function which will train the Naive Bayes Model i.e compute a BoW for each

category/class.

Returns:

Nothing"

```
self.examples=dataset
```

```
self.labels=labels
```

```
self.bow_dicts=np.array([defaultdict(lambda:0) for index in  
range(self.classes.shape[0])])
```

```
#only convert to numpy arrays if initially not passed as numpy arrays - else  
its a useless recomputation
```

```
if not isinstance(self.examples,np.ndarray):  
self.examples=np.array(self.examples)
```

```
if not isinstance(self.labels,np.ndarray): self.labels=np.array(self.labels)
```

```

#constructing BoW for each category
for cat_index,cat in enumerate(self.classes):
    all_cat_examples=self.examples[self.labels==cat] #filter all examples of
category == cat
    #get examples preprocessed
    cleaned_examples=[preprocess_string(cat_example) for cat_example in
all_cat_examples]
    cleaned_examples=pd.DataFrame(data=cleaned_examples)
    #now construct BoW of this particular category
    np.apply_along_axis(self.addToBow,1,cleaned_examples,cat_index)
def f(row):
    """This function returns sentiment value based on the overall ratings from the
user"""
    if row['overall'] == 3.0:
        val = 'malicious'
    elif row['overall'] == 1.0 or row['overall'] == 2.0:
        val = 'Negative'
    elif row['overall'] == 4.0 or row['overall'] == 5.0:
        val = 'Positive'
    else:
        val = -1
    return val
#Applying the function in our new column
process_reviews['sentiment'] = process_reviews.apply(f, axis=1)
process_reviews.head()
#setiment vs helpfulrate
pd.DataFrame(process_reviews.groupby('sentiment')['helpful_rate'].mean())
#plot layout
plt.rcParams.update({'font.size': 18})

```

```

rcParams['figure.figsize'] = 16,9

# Creating dataframe and removing 0 helpfulrate records

senti_help= pd.DataFrame(process_reviews, columns = ['sentiment',
'helpful_rate'])

senti_help = senti_help[senti_help['helpful_rate'] != 0.00]

#Plotting phase

sns.violinplot( x=senti_help["sentiment"], y=senti_help["helpful_rate"])

plt.title('Sentiment vs Helpfulness')

plt.xlabel('Sentiment categories')

plt.ylabel('helpful rate')

plt.show()

//Accuracy rate value of algorithm model compared with few other algorithm
models

def compare_models():

    print("\n\nPlease wait. This may take a few minutes")

    print("\nAnalyzing Ensemble Classifier")

    lr_model = LogisticRegression()

    lr_model.fit(X_train_data_new,Y_train_data)

    predictions['EnsembleClassification'] = lr_model.predict(x_test_data_new)

    print("\nAnalyzing Multinomial")

    mul_model = MultinomialNB()

    mul_model.fit(X_train_data_new,Y_train_data)

    predictions["Multinomial"] = mul_model.predict(x_test_data_new)

    print("\nAnalyzing Bernoulli")

    ber_model = BernoulliNB()

    ber_model.fit(X_train_data_new,Y_train_data)

    predictions["Bernoulli"]=ber_model.predict(x_test_

```

```

data_new)

print("\nAnalyzing Decision Tree")

tree_model = tree.DecisionTreeClassifier()

tree_model.fit(X_train_data_new,Y_train_data)

predictions["DecisionTree"] = tree_model.predict(x_test_data_new)

print("\nAnalyzing Naive Bayes Classifier")

ess_model = RandomForestClassifier()

ess_model.fit(X_train_data_new,Y_train_data)

predictions["Naive Bayes"] = ess_model.predict(x_test_data_new)

print("\nAnalyzing SVM")

svm_model = SVC()

svm_model.fit(X_train_data_new,Y_train_data)

predictions['SVM']=svm_model.predict(x_test_data_new)

print("\nAnalyzing k-NN")

knn_model = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=1)

knn_model.fit(X_train_data_new,Y_train_data)

predictions["knn"] = knn_model.predict(x_test_data_new)

print("\n\nCalculating Accuracy of each model.\n\n")

#Model Accuracy Table

print_results = { }

for k,v in predictions.items():

    print_results[k] = accuracy_score(y_test_data,v)

result_table=pd.DataFrame(list(print_results.items()),

```

```
columns=["Model","Accuracy"])

print(result_table)

#Bar chart comparing accuracies of models

plt.figure(figsize= (10,8))

sns.barplot(x = "Model", y = "Accuracy", data = result_table)

plt.title("Model accuracy")

plt.xticks(rotation = 90)
```

B. SCREENSHOTS

PRE-PROCESSING

//sample dataset

```
In [181]: raw_reviews.head()
```

Out[181]:

	reviewerID	asin	reviewerName	helpful	reviewText	overall	summary	unixReviewTime	reviewTime
0	A2IBPI20UZIR0U	1384719342	cassandra tu "Yeah, well, that's just like, u...	[0, 0]	Not much to write about here, but it does exac...	5	good	1393545600	02 28, 2014
1	A14VAT5EAX3D9S	1384719342	Jake	[13, 14]	The product does exactly as it should and is q...	5	Jake	1363392000	03 16, 2013
2	A195EZSQDW3E21	1384719342	Rick Bennette "Rick Bennette"	[1, 1]	The primary job of this device is to block the...	5	It Does The Job Well	1377648000	08 28, 2013
3	A2C00NNG1ZQQG2	1384719342	RustyBill "Sunday Rocker"	[0, 0]	Nice windscreen protects my MXL mic and preven...	5	GOOD WINDSCREEN FOR THE MONEY	1392336000	02 14, 2014
4	A94QU4C90B1AX	1384719342	SEAN MASLANKA	[0, 0]	This pop filter is great. It looks and perform...	5	No more pops when I record my vocals.	1392940800	02 21, 2014

//Eliminating disturbed data's

```
In [12]: print(stop_words)
```

['%', '*', 'unselv', 'itwaen', 'weit', 'siaf', 'ts', 'ase', 'qf', 'isalf', 'ere', 'un', 'eih', 'e', 'nnodu', 'ihct', 'kfe', 'jl e', 'hn', 'nsk', 'kai', 'aadu', 'varta', 'y', 'isn', 'fsjuy', 'fep', 'oau', 'nv', 'lrd', 'ila', 'uvs', 'gb', 'rw', 'jxa', 'kj u', 'iva', 'sda', 'katu', 'mla', 'ip', 'kq', 'bw', 'cx', 'gl', 'oyz', 'lq', 'oz', 'shjf', 'jcb', 'pta', 'hl', 'aun', 'uhb', 'kh fsgvt', 'rhyx', 'ilak', 'vsiu', 'ksnu', 'ku', 'qm', 'unavu', 'pwq', 'xc', 'wdu', 'ln', 'obq', 'dc', 'en', 'kip', 'lta', 'azz', 'pz', 'nz', '^', '!\$', 'jik', 'hj', 'kaal', 'lsr', 'udu', 'fk', 'fl', 'qd', 'ial', 'iru', 'jna', 'kti', 'cela', 've', 'd', 'r a', 'fthr', 'u', 'you', 'lou', 'oan', 'ece', 'aen', 'of', 'avd', 'ann', 'ore', 'ngi', 'yenga', 'ivunga', 'nee', 'vaa', 'c', 'ye na', 'ipi', 'ayl', '@', '#']

```
In [189]: process_reviews.head()
```

Out[189]:

	reviewerID	asin	helpful	reviewText	overall	summary	reviewTime
0	A2IBPI20UZIR0U	1384719342	[0, 0]	Not much to write about here, but it does exac...	5	good	02 28, 2014
1	A14VAT5EAX3D9S	1384719342	[13, 14]	The product does exactly as it should and is q...	5	Jake	03 16, 2013
2	A195EZSQDW3E21	1384719342	[1, 1]	The primary job of this device is to block the...	5	It Does The Job Well	08 28, 2013
3	A2C00NNG1ZQQG2	1384719342	[0, 0]	Nice windscreen protects my MXL mic and preven...	5	GOOD WINDSCREEN FOR THE MONEY	02 14, 2014
4	A94QU4C90B1AX	1384719342	[0, 0]	This pop filter is great. It looks and perform...	5	No more pops when I record my vocals.	02 21, 2014

FEATURE EXTRACTION

//Dimensionality-reduction of data's

// Before Dimensionality-reduction process

```
process_reviews.head()
```

Out[14]:

	reviewerID	asin	helpful	reviewText	overall	summary	date	year
0	A2IBPI20UZIR0U	1384719342	[0, 0]	Not much to write about here, but it does exac...	5	good	02 28	2014
1	A14VAT5EAX3D9S	1384719342	[13, 14]	The product does exactly as it should and is q...	5	Jake	03 16	2013
2	A195EZSQDW3E21	1384719342	[1, 1]	The primary job of this device is to block the...	5	It Does The Job Well	08 28	2013
3	A2C00NNG1ZQQG2	1384719342	[0, 0]	Nice windscreen protects my MXL mic and preven...	5	GOOD WINDSCREEN FOR THE MONEY	02 14	2014
4	A94QU4C90B1AX	1384719342	[0, 0]	This pop filter is great. It looks and perform...	5	No more pops when I record my vocals.	02 21	2014

//After Dimensionality-reduction process

```
process_reviews.head()
```

Out[17]:

	reviewerID	asin	helpful	overall	date	year	reviews
0	A2IBPI20UZIR0U	1384719342	[0, 0]	5	02 28	2014	Not much to write about here, but it does exac...
1	A14VAT5EAX3D9S	1384719342	[13, 14]	5	03 16	2013	The product does exactly as it should and is q...
2	A195EZSQDW3E21	1384719342	[1, 1]	5	08 28	2013	The primary job of this device is to block the...
3	A2C00NNG1ZQQG2	1384719342	[0, 0]	5	02 14	2014	Nice windscreen protects my MXL mic and preven...
4	A94QU4C90B1AX	1384719342	[0, 0]	5	02 21	2014	This pop filter is great. It looks and perform...

CLASSIFICATION

//output of malicious reviews with positive and negative from trained dataset

//compare algorithms

Compare Models

Click

Please wait. This may take a few minutes

Analyzing Ensemble Classifier

Analyzing Multinomial

Analyzing Bernoulli

Analyzing Decision Tree

Analyzing Naive Bayes Classifier

Analyzing SVM

Analyzing k-NN

Calculating Accuracy of each model.

	Model	Accuracy
0	EnsembleClassification	0.946875
1	Multinomial	0.927375
2	Bernoulli	0.811888
3	DecisionTree	0.941588
4	Naive Bayes	0.966125
5	SVM	0.943625
6	knn	0.934888

//output of analyze each model

Analyze each model

Click

Classifier Model

Naive Bayes

- Accuracy
- ROC Curve
- Precision, Recall and F-Measure

Submit

Naive Bayes Classifier
Please be patient. This may take some time.
Accuracy = 0.964

Naive Bayes Classifier
Please be patient. This may take some time.

Naive Bayes Classifier
Please be patient. This may take some time.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Good	0.97	0.96	0.96	4045
Bad	0.96	0.97	0.96	3955
accuracy			0.96	8000
macro avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	8000
weighted avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	8000

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